

attributed the bands at 3 460, 3 330 and 3 180 cm^{-1} to secondary $-\text{NHCSNH}_2$ group. The spectra of the thiosemicarbazones of substituted salicylaldehydes show similar bands. The SH stretch in mercaptans and thiophenols absorbs¹⁵ at 2 590–2 540 cm^{-1} . Due to the greater mass of sulphur the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ is expected to occur at considerably lower frequencies than the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vibration in the C–O or C–N region. This means that the C=S and the attached single bonds can interact with the result that more than one band involves C=S stretch¹⁶. Gingras *et al.*¹⁷ attributed the band at 1 130–1 080 cm^{-1} in the spectra of several thiosemicarbazones to the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ because the band in this region disappears on complex formation. A simple calculation of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ by using Gordy's rule and harmonic oscillation equation gave a value of 6×10^5 dyne cm^{-1} for the stretching force constant, corresponding to 1 080 cm^{-1} . A more accurate calculation predicts C=S stretching modes¹⁶ at 1 450, 1 059 and 757 cm^{-1} . The absorption in the region 830–805 cm^{-1} in spectra of thiosemicarbazones should be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$. The 1 532 cm^{-1} band is assigned¹⁸ as mainly $\nu_{\text{CN}+\delta\text{NH}_2}$.

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Potentiometric Studies on some Ternary Complexes of Neodymium(III)

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IN continuation of our previous work on complexation equilibria of lanthanides^{1,2}, the present paper reports the binary complexation behaviour of Nd^{III} with suberic acid $[\text{HOOC}(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{COOH}]$ (SA) and azelaic acid $[\text{HOOC}(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{COOH}]$ (AA) and ternary $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}-\text{HEDTA}-(\text{SA or AA})$ equilibria at 25° and $\mu=0.1 M \text{KNO}_3$. The ternary equilibria were also studied at two other temperatures 5 and 45° at $\mu=0.1 M \text{KNO}_3$. The effects of change in dielectric constant and ionic strength have also been studied.

Experimental

Solutions of HEDTA (Sigma), SA (Fluka, A.G.) and AA (Fluka, A.G.) were prepared in oxygen-free double-distilled water and were standardised potentiometrically by titrating with sodium hydroxide solution³. All other reagents were of A.R. grade. Nd^{III} solution was standardised by EDTA method⁴.

Procedure for the pH-metric study of binary systems was the same as described earlier⁵ maintaining a metal-ligand ratio of 1:5 except that instead of perchloric acid, nitric acid was used in the present case. For mixed ligand systems the procedure was the same as described earlier⁶. To

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study the effect of change in dielectric constant different percentages (30, 40, 50 and 60%) of ethanol and methanol were used. The effect of change in ionic strength was carried out by studying mixed ligand complex systems at different ionic strengths (0.05, 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2 M KNO₃) at 25°.

methanol and ethanol indicates that ion-ion interaction between metal ion and anionic oxygen donor ligand is greater than ion-dipole interaction between the metal and solvent molecules as the dipole moments of the molecules decrease°. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constant values

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS UNDER DIFFERENT CONDITIONS AT 25°

System*	Constant	Stability constant at different ionic strength				Stability constant at different solvent composition** (μ=0.1 M)			
		0.05 M	0.1 M	0.15 M	0.2 M	30%	40%	50%	60%
SA	log K ₁ ^H	5.00	4.95	4.85	4.80	5.85 (5.85)	(6.05)	6.05 (6.10)	6.15 (6.25)
	log K ₂ ^H	4.15	4.02	3.95	3.88	4.65 (4.85)	(4.95)	5.05 (5.05)	5.25 (5.25)
AA	log K ₁ ^H	5.45	5.20	5.15	5.05	5.60 (5.95)	5.65 (6.10)	5.65 (6.30)	
	log K ₂ ^H	4.35	4.09	4.05	3.95	4.15 (4.95)	4.35 (5.15)	4.70 (5.30)	
[Nd ^{III} -SA]	log K _{ML} ^M		4.55						
[Nd ^{III} -AA]	log K _{ML} ^M		4.70						
[Nd ^{III} -HEDTA-SA]	log K _{MAL} ^{MA}	4.07	3.54	3.50	3.37	3.86 (4.70)	3.95 (5.08)	4.10 (5.45)	5.21
[Nd ^{III} -HEDTA-AA]	log K _{MAL} ^{MA}	3.90	3.84	3.59	3.47	4.46 (4.39)	5.23 (4.37)	5.20 (5.04)	(5.30)

*Charge omitted.

**Values given in parenthesis are those for water-ethanol media.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were evaluated by analysing the pH-titration curves according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁷ and Bhattacharya⁸. [Nd^{III}-HEDTA] complex formation starts at lower pH and the formation is completed at pH ~4.0. The $\bar{n}$ values remain unchanged upto pH ~8, indicating that [Nd^{III}-HEDTA] formed at lower pH is stable and does not undergo hydrolysis upto pH ~10. Formation of [Nd^{III}-SA] and [Nd^{III}-AA] starts at pH ~7.5 and ~6.5, respectively. The formation is completed at pH ~9.

In the formation of ternary [Nd^{III}-HEDTA-SA] and [Nd^{III}-HEDTA-AA] complexes, the $\bar{n}$ values reached upto ~0.8. Since the [Nd^{III}-HEDTA] complex was very stable, there was no possibility of any replacement reaction. The stability constant of [Nd^{III}-HEDTA] complex is much greater than that with SA and AA obviously due to the pentadentate nature of HEDTA as against bidentate nature of SA and AA ligands. In Nd^{III}-HEDTA-(SA or AA) ternary complexes, HEDTA occupies five-coordinating positions and SA or AA occupy two coordinating positions, thus Nd^{III} exhibits a coordination number of seven.

Stability constants increase with the increase in percentage of non-aqueous solvents (Table 1). Linear variation of log K with mole fraction of

decrease with the increase in ionic strength. Plots of $\sqrt{\mu}$ vs proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants are linear proving the validity of Bronsted equation¹⁰.

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